

Enhancing the stability of sodium-ion capacitors by introducing glyoxylic-acetal based electrolyte

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ABSTRACT

Sodium-ion Capacitors (SICs) are becoming increasingly important energy storage devices. This study presents an in-depth comparison of a largely used electrolyte for said application, sodium hexafluorophosphate in ethylene carbonate:propylene carbonate (NaPF₆ in EC:PC), with the novel electrolyte sodium bis(tri-fluoromethanesulfonyl)imide in 1,1,2,2-tetraethoxyethane:propylene carbonate (NaTFSI in TEG:PC). Firstly, half-cells of the SIC standard electrode materials, hard carbon (HC) and activated carbon (AC), are shown to perform comparably well with the two electrolytes. However, the use of the novel electrolyte in SICs allows for an improved stability during float tests. All in all, the novel electrolyte NaTFSI in TEG:PC appears to be a very promising alternative electrolyte for SIC application.

1. Introduction

The importance of electrochemical energy storage devices (EES) in our society increased enormously in the last years and, nowadays, these devices are essential for our daily lives. EES are used in a very large number of different applications, which require different times of charging/discharging. Electrochemical capacitors (EC) are the most important high-power systems and they are currently used in many applications [1]. However, the low energy density of these devices (<10 W h kg⁻¹) is limiting their use, especially in the automotive sector [2]. With the goal to increase the energy density of ECs, researchers developed the concept of metal-ion capacitors (MICs). Here, one capacitive type electrode (used in EC) is combined with a faradaic type electrode (used in rechargeable batteries) [3]. The combination of the fast capacitive and the high-capacity faradic storage mechanism leads to a device which theoretically combines both high power and high energy density [4]. The *state-of-the-art* MICs, i.e. lithium-ion capacitors, are already commercially available [5]. However, when aiming for a sustainable energy sector, one also must consider the implications of the production of the EES. Lithium is quite scarce and distributed very inhomogeneously on the crust of the Earth [6]. Therefore, relying solely on this metal for the realization of EES is not advisable, neither from an economical nor an ecological perspective [7]. An obvious alternative for lithium is its direct neighbor in the periodic table: Sodium. The element

combines abundance and interesting (electro)chemical behavior. Thus, sodium-ion capacitors (SICs) were developed. Although the interest in SICs increased significantly in the last years, this technology has not entered the commercial market yet [8]. Currently, most of the investigated SICs contain hard carbon (HC) as the battery material negative electrode and activated carbon (AC) as the capacitive material positive electrode [8]. As electrolyte 1 M sodium hexafluorophosphate (NaPF₆) in ethylene carbonate:propylene carbonate (EC:PC) is commonly being used [9]. Although this electrolyte is featuring good properties and its usage allows for good performance, alternative electrolytes need to be investigated which might enhance the safety of the device. The fluorine content of NaPF₆ is very high compared to other sodium salts when normalized on the mass. Fluorine is often regarded as necessary for forming a stable SEI but it also entails significant environmental and safety issues [10]. Therefore, attempts are being made to reduce the fluorine content and still obtain stable systems.

In the past years our group investigated the use of glyoxylic-acetal based solvents in energy storage devices [11–15]. We showed that by utilizing these commercially available and cheap solvents, it is possible to formulate electrolytes with good transport and thermal properties as well as comparably low fluorine content. Studies about lithium-ion, sodium-ion and potassium-ion batteries containing glyoxylic-acetal based electrolytes have been published [15–18]. Furthermore, we demonstrated a *proof-of-concept* implementing those novel electrolytes

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in SICs [18]. In the present study, we show an in depth-comparison between the “conventional” 1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC and the glyoxal-based electrolyte 1 M sodium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide in 1,1,2,2-tetraethoxyethane:propylene carbonate (NaTFSI in TEG:PC). The choice of reference (NaPF₆ in EC:PC) was made in order to compare the novel to the *state-of-the-art* electrolyte and highlight its competitiveness to a well-known benchmark. In the first part of the study the use of these two electrolytes in combination with HC and AC electrodes is investigated. In the second part, their impact on the performance and floating stability of SICs is considered in detail.

2. Experimental

2.1. Electrode preparation

For hard carbon (HC) and activated carbon (AC) electrodes a mass ratio of 90 wt% active material (AM) to 5 wt% binder to 5 wt% conducting agent was chosen. Independently of the used active material Na-Carboxymethyl cellulose (Na-CMC, CRT2000 GA, Walocel) was used as binder and carbon black (CB, C-ENERGY™ Super C45, Imerys) as conducting agent. The AC (YP-50F) and HC (Biocarbon-5 μm) were provided by Kuraray. All the solids were weighed in and mixed with three parts deionized water. The mixture was processed for 3 min at 50 oscillation per second in a ball mill. Using the doctor-blade technique films of 100 μm (for HC) and 150 μm (for AC) were manufactured onto an etched aluminum-foil. After drying overnight at room temperature, electrodes with a surface area of 1.13 cm² were punched. The electrodes were dried at 0.5 mbar at 60 °C overnight and then inserted into an argon filled glovebox (Mbraun, O₂ and H₂O < 1 ppm). The mass loading of the electrodes containing HC was ~1.9 mg cm⁻², while that of the electrodes containing AC was ~2.8 mg cm⁻².

When the AC electrodes were tested in half-cells, oversized AC-electrodes were used as the counter electrodes (CEs). A mass ratio of AM 90 wt%, conducting agent 5 wt% and binder 5 wt% was chosen. 100 mg of AC YP-50F (Kuraray), 5.6 mg of CB and 9.3 mg of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, 60 wt% in H₂O, Sigma Aldrich) were weighed in and suspended in ethanol (EtOH). Whilst stirring, EtOH was steadily added to form a viscous material. The slurry was rolled out to a thin film with a glass bar and folded back up again for multiple times. When needed to maintain the smoothness of the film, a few drops of EtOH were added. Finally, the mixture was rolled out to a thin film and electrodes with a diameter of 12 mm were punched. The electrodes were dried overnight at 60 °C and 0.1 mbar. The mass loading of the electrodes was ~20 mg cm⁻².

2.2. Electrolyte preparation

The solvent 1,1,2,2-tetraethoxyethane (tetraethoxyglyoxal, TEG) was supplied by WeylChem. The initial water content of TEG was reduced to ≤20 ppm by filtering over dried aluminum oxide (90 active basic, Merck) under argon atmosphere. The water content was determined via Karl-Fischer titration (C20 Coulometric KF Titrator, METTLER TOLEDO). Propylene carbonate (PC, anhydrous 99.7 %, Sigma Aldrich) was dried over molar sieves to reduce the water content below 10 ppm and used without further purification. The conducting salt sodium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (NaTFSI) was purchased from Solvionic and used without further purification. The electrolyte 1 M NaTFSI in TEG:PC (3:7, wt) was prepared in a glovebox. The electrolyte 1 M NaPF₆ in EC:PC (1:1, wt) was provided by E-lyte (<10 ppm water content) and used without further purification. In the following the electrolytes will be indicated as NaTFSI in TEG:PC and NaPF₆ in EC:PC.

2.3. Electrolyte characterization

The viscosity was measured in the temperature range between -10 and 80 °C at an Anton-Paar MCR 102 rotational viscometer, applying a

shear rate of 1000 s⁻¹. For conductivity measurements, 0.5 mL of electrolyte were added into a sealed glass cell with two parallel platinized platinum electrodes having a known cell constant (*ca.* 1 cm⁻¹, examined with KCl solution). The cell was placed into a climate chamber (BINDER) for electrochemical impedance measurement (amplitude: 5 mV, frequency range: 100 mHz–100 MHz) using a ModulabXM ECS potentiostat (Solartron) to obtain the alternating current resistance and calculate the electrolyte conductivity. The density values were measured by using a density meter DMA 4100 M (Anton Paar) between 0 and 80 °C.

2.4. Assembly of half-cells: preliminary investigations

Swagelok-cells were assembled in an argon filled glovebox. As a separator a glass fiber disk (Whatman GF/D) soaked with 150 μL of electrolytic solution was used.

For the investigation of the HC-electrodes metallic sodium was used as CE and RE (three-electrode set-up). In galvanostatic cycling with potential limitations (GCPL)-measurements the performance at different C-rates was tested between 5 mV and 2 V vs. Na⁺/Na. One discharge/charge cycle of 0.05 C was employed to form the SEI. Afterwards five cycles at each rate (0.1 C, 0.5 C, 1 C, 2 C, 5 C, 10 C) were carried out followed by another 10 cycles at 0.1 C. Note that 1 C = 372 mA g⁻¹. The stability was investigated by charging/discharging the electrodes for 1000 cycles at 1 C. The measurements were performed at a LBT21084 multichannel potentiostatic-galvanostatic system (Arbin Instruments).

For the investigations of the AC electrodes an oversized AC electrode was used as CE and sodium metal as RE. The cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were performed at 10 and 100 mV s⁻¹ between 2 and 4 V vs. Na⁺/Na. The rate capability was determined within the same voltage range at current densities of 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20 A g⁻¹ for ten cycles each. The cycling stability was tested for 10000 cycles at 2 A g⁻¹. For these measurements a BioLogic VMP-3 and a BioLogic MPG-2 potentiostat were utilized.

The anodic dissolution of the aluminum current collector was investigated utilizing half-cells containing Al as WE and Na as CE and RE. The Al was charged with 1 mV s⁻¹ up to 4 V vs. Na⁺/Na, the potential was held for 3 h. Afterwards, the electrode was discharged to 2 V vs. Na⁺/Na. The procedure was repeated ten times. The same test was also carried out using 3.8 V vs. Na⁺/Na as the upper potential limit.

Floating tests of both AC and HC half-cells were conducted. AC half-cells were assembled with oversized AC as CE and Na as RE. The electrode was activated by cycling between 2 and 3.8 V vs. Na⁺/Na for 10 cycles at 50 mA g⁻¹ followed by 200 cycles at 400 mA g⁻¹. The potential of 3.8 V vs. Na⁺/Na was held for 5 h and in between charge/discharge cycles at 100 mA g⁻¹ were performed. A total of 200 h of float time was done. For HC half-cells 10 cycles of activation at 50 mA g⁻¹ were performed between 5 mV and 2 V vs. Na⁺/Na. The potential of 5 mV vs. Na⁺/Na was held for 5 h and in between charge/discharge cycles at 100 mA g⁻¹ were conducted. Overall, the HC electrodes were floated for 100 h.

2.5. Assembly of half-cells: pre-treatment before SIC assembly

As presodiation step, a HC electrode was precycled in a separate half-cell (three-electrode set-up, Na as CE and RE), before assembling a SIC. Precisely, the electrode was discharged at 0.05 C for 3 h, followed by a discharge of 0.1 C until 5 mV vs. Na⁺/Na were reached. The potential of 5 mV was held for 1 h. Subsequently, the HC was charged up to 2.5 V vs. Na⁺/Na at 0.1 C and discharged to 5 mV vs. Na⁺/Na at 0.025 C. The HC was then charged to 2 V vs. Na⁺/Na by 0.1 C and discharged at the same rate. Another five cycles of charge/discharge at 0.1 C followed. The final potential of 5 mV vs. Na⁺/Na was held until ≤30 % of 0.1 C of current was flowing which took around 2 h. For this GCPL-measurement a BioLogic VMP-3 or BioLogic MPG-2 potentiostat was utilized. Normally, the HC potential upon disconnection was between 50 mV and 150 mV

vs. Na^+/Na , depending on the IR-drop and the timing. The cell was disassembled in the glovebox and the presodiated HC-electrode was inserted into the SIC device.

2.6. Assembly of SIC full-cells

In a three-electrode set-up, the presodiated HC was combined with an AC electrode and metallic sodium. Before starting the SIC measurement, the uncycled AC electrode needed to be charged to realize a broad cell voltage window. For that purpose, the AC electrode was *in-situ* connected to the sodium metal as CE/RE. The AC was then brought to 4.0 V vs. Na^+/Na , using current densities of 250 or 500 mA g^{-1} . The potential was held for 30 min. Then, the AC-electrode was connected as WE (positive electrode), the HC-electrode as CE (negative electrode) and Na as RE and the SIC device was tested galvanostatically between $1 \text{ V} < E_{\text{cell}} < 3.8 \text{ V}$. Current densities of 25, 50, 100, 250 and 500 mA g^{-1} were applied. Note that the current rate was normalized on the sum of both electrodes' active material masses. For determining the stability, float measurements have been performed. First, ten activation cycles at 0.1 A g^{-1} were conducted, followed by a resting time of 10 h. In a loop five cycles at 0.1 A g^{-1} , 5 h of float at $E_{\text{cell}} = 3.8 \text{ V}$ and 5 h of resting time were applied for 24 times resulting in a total floating time of 120 h. The measurements were performed at a BioLogic VMP-3 or a BioLogic MPG-2 potentiostat.

2.7. Data evaluation

The specifics of the electrochemical data evaluation can be found in the supporting information (see Fig. S1).

2.8. Post-mortem XPS

After floating for 120 h, the SICs were discharged to 1 V and disassembled in a glovebox. The electrodes of the SIC containing NaPF_6 in EC:PC were washed by submersing them for 1 min in PC to remove salt residues from the surface. For the electrodes floated in SICs containing NaTFSI in TEG:PC the same procedure was performed using TEG:PC (3:7, wt) as the solvent mixture. Subsequently the electrodes were dried at 0.5 mbar and 40 °C and stored in a glovebox.

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted using a Thermo Scientific KAlpha spectrometer equipped with an Al $K\alpha$ anode ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$). The chamber pressure during the measurements was kept below 5×10^{-8} mbar. A flood gun was used to compensate surface charges due to lower electric conductivity of post-mortem electrodes. The gun was calibrated to the C-C binding energy in polyethylene at 284.8 eV. Survey scans for elemental composition analysis were

recorded between 0 and 1350 eV with a step size of 1 eV and a pass energy of 1050 eV. High resolution spectra were recorded with a step size of 0.05 eV and a pass energy of 30 eV. The measurement spot size was 400 μm and each HR spectrum was recorded as a sum of 5 scans. Since all samples contained carbon and a flood gun was used, C1s spectra were not shifted to 284.8 eV. Samples were put on adhesive copper foil prior to the measurement. Peak fitting was done using the Advantage software of Thermo Fischer Scientific. The "Smart" background function was used to fit the binding energies of the HR spectra. Peaks are assigned according to the NIST database.

3. Results

3.1. Physicochemical properties of the investigated electrolytes

Firstly, the physicochemical properties of the selected electrolytes were investigated. In Fig. 1a the resulting conductivity values are shown. It is evident that NaPF_6 in EC:PC has the higher conductivity values in the entire temperature range between $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At room temperature ($20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) NaPF_6 in EC:PC displays a conductivity of 7.8 mS cm^{-1} , while the one of NaTFSI in TEG:PC is 3.0 mS cm^{-1} . The ion mobility is thus higher in the "conventional" electrolyte. This is especially important for high-power application. It is thus expected that NaPF_6 in EC:PC works up to higher current densities compared to NaTFSI in TEG:PC. The NaPF_6 in EC:PC electrolyte is also less viscous than NaTFSI in TEG:PC (Fig. 1b). At $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ NaPF_6 in EC:PC displays a viscosity of 5.4 mPa s, while NaTFSI in TEG:PC shows a value of 9.9 mPa s. The density (Fig. S2) of NaPF_6 in EC:PC is slightly higher than the one of NaTFSI in TEG:PC in the temperature range between $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the density of NaPF_6 in EC:PC is 1.34 g cm^{-3} , while the one of NaTFSI in TEG:PC is 1.25 g cm^{-3} . The lower density of NaTFSI in TEG:PC signifies a lower mass of the device compared to a cell in which the same volume of NaPF_6 in EC:PC is used, which is naturally an advantage in application. Overall, both electrolytes display promising physicochemical in accordance with literature [18,19].

3.2. Half-cell studies

Before investigating the SIC full-cells, the electrochemical behavior of HC (Fig. 2a–d) and AC (Fig. 3a–c) in NaTFSI in TEG:PC and in NaPF_6 in EC:PC was studied.

Fig. 2a and b compare the differential capacities of HC electrodes in the two electrolytes NaPF_6 in EC:PC (a) and NaTFSI in TEG:PC (b). The first cycle (at 0.05 C) and the fourth cycle (at 0.1 C) are displayed. Insets magnifying the most relevant potential regions i) 0–0.2 V and ii) 0.4–1.3 V vs. Na^+/Na are also shown. It is apparent that the HC electrodes

Fig. 1. Physicochemical properties of investigated electrolytes. Conductivity (a) and viscosity (b) of NaPF_6 in EC:PC and NaTFSI in TEG:PC.

Fig. 2. Electrochemical results of HC half-cells. Differential capacity with respective electrolytes NaPF₆ in EC:PC (a) and NaTFSI in TEG:PC (b), rate-test (c) and cycling test (d).

behave quite similarly with the two electrolytes, thus, the graphs will be discussed together. During the first sodiation process the curves show a bulge at 0.9 V vs. Na^+/Na . This capacity can probably be assigned to the SEI-formation. Below 0.1 V vs. Na^+/Na large capacity peaks can be seen. The discharge peak is located at 60 mV and the charge at 90 mV vs. Na^+/Na . At those potentials Na^+ ions are (de)intercalated into the HC structure. The differential capacity during cycle four shows a significantly less distinct peak at 0.9 V vs. Na^+/Na . Consequently, it is reasonable to suppose that the SEI-formation has been completed before the fourth cycle (as expected). However, it has to be mentioned that the different C-rates make a quantitative analysis of the differential capacity values difficult. The peaks associated to the sodiation process in cycle four are slightly shifted to 40 mV (compared to the initial 60 mV vs. Na^+/Na). For the charge process less significant changes between the cycle numbers can be seen. The differential capacity is decreased slightly $\sim 700 \text{ mA h g}^{-1} \text{V}^{-1}$ and the peaks are shifted to higher potentials (0.1 V instead of 0.09 V vs. Na^+/Na). In terms of the different electrolytes almost no difference is seen. Overall the NaPF₆ in EC:PC system shows a broader peak and can thus deliver slightly more capacity.

To investigate the performances of the electrodes at higher rates, a rate-capability test was conducted. As shown in Fig. 2c the performances of the electrolytes are quite comparable. Both systems are stable and at the lowest C-rate of 0.1 C display capacities around $\sim 250 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$. The initial coulombic efficiency (ICE) is 75 % for the NaTFSI in TEG:PC device and 80 % for the NaPF₆ EC:PC system, thus also not significantly different. It is noteworthy that for the higher rates, namely 2 C, 5 C and 10 C, the NaPF₆ in EC:PC system shows higher capacity values. For high-power devices such as SICs, the high-rate performance is of the utmost importance. For 5 C the NaTFSI in TEG:PC system displays capacity

values around 20 mA h g^{-1} and for 10 C the capacity is approximately zero. After the rate-test ten cycles at 0.1 C were conducted to verify the principal stability of the devices. Both display stable capacities. However, it can be seen that the NaTFSI in TEG:PC system shows coulombic efficiencies of around 97 % while the NaPF₆ in EC:PC values are >99 %. The rate-test behavior is thus quite comparable but for higher rates the NaPF₆ in EC:PC device performs better. This is not surprising considering the more favorable transport properties of this electrolyte compared to the glyoxylic-acetal based one, as discussed above. Aside from the high-rate performance, another important feature of SICs is their long cycle-life. Hence, the stability of the HC electrodes was also investigated by cycling them at 1 C for 1000 cycles. To ensure proper wetting and activation, five precycles at 0.1 C were carried out. Fig. 2d compares the stability of the HC electrodes in the two electrolytes. As shown, both systems display high capacity retention values considering HC is a battery-type material. However, it is interesting to notice that the electrode cycled in NaTFSI in TEG:PC displays a longer cycle life (>1000 cycles) compared to the one cycled in NaPF₆ in EC:PC (~ 500 cycles).

Fig. 3 compares the electrochemical performance of AC-based electrodes in the investigated electrolytes. Fig. 3a shows the voltametric profiles between 2 and 4 V vs. Na^+/Na of the electrodes at 10 mV s^{-1} (solid line). For both systems rather rectangular CV-curves are obtained. The electrodes thus display the typical capacitive behavior, indicating the formation of a double layer at the electrode-electrolyte interface. The capacitance values at high potentials are very comparable for both electrolytes ($\sim 120 \text{ F g}^{-1}$). At low potentials (2 V vs. Na^+/Na), however, the AC cycled in NaPF₆ in EC:PC displays higher capacitance values (-97 F g^{-1} vs. -77 F g^{-1}). This indicates that the mobility as well as the ion-ion interactions within the electrolytes is different. At a much higher

Fig. 3. Electrochemical results of AC half-cells. CV (a), rate-test (b) and cycling test (c).

scan rate of 100 $mV s^{-1}$ (dashed line) the same observations can be made: The electrode with NaPF₆ in EC:PC displays a more capacitive behavior (indicated by the more rectangular shape) and overall features higher capacitance values. Fig. 3b compares the capacitance retention displayed by the electrodes. At first glance it is obvious that the AC cycled in NaPF₆ in EC:PC shows higher capacitance values throughout all applied current densities (0.1–20 $A g^{-1}$). At 0.1 $A g^{-1}$ the electrode displays 80 $F g^{-1}$ which decreases only slightly to 74 $F g^{-1}$ at an increased current density of 10 $A g^{-1}$. Thus, around 93 % of the initial

capacitance at the low rate were still accessible at the higher rate. On the other hand, the AC electrode tested with NaTFSI in TEG:PC displays 73 $F g^{-1}$ at 0.1 $A g^{-1}$ and 49 $F g^{-1}$ at 10 $A g^{-1}$ corresponding to a capacitance retention of 67 %. Overall, NaTFSI in TEG:PC performs well up to a current density of 2 $A g^{-1}$. At higher current rates the capacitance diminishes significantly. In this measurement much higher current densities than for the HC investigation were applied (maximum 20 $A g^{-1}$ for AC vs. 3.74 $A g^{-1}$ for HC). At those very high rates the kinetic limitation of NaTFSI in TEG:PC due to the lower conductivity becomes much more evident.

Fig. 3c shows the capacitance retention displayed by the AC electrodes after 10000 cycles carried out at 2 $A g^{-1}$. Both systems are very stable, and at the end of the test the AC electrode cycled in NaPF₆ in EC:PC retains 98 % of its initial capacitance, while the one cycled in NaTFSI in TEG:PC retains 92 % of its initial capacitance.

For SIC application it is very important to maximize the cell voltage window in order to gain energy density [8]. The negative cut-off potential is limited by plating which should be prevented for the sake of safety. The positive cut-off potential is thus the main parameter that can be optimized. Naturally, the electrolyte should be electrochemically stable at the upper cut-off potential to ensure high cycle life. Furthermore, high potentials entail the danger of anodic dissolution of the aluminum current collector. In this regard imide-based electrolytes are known to show said issues at potentials approaching 4.0 V vs. Na^+/Na [20]. Since herein an imide-based electrolyte has been employed, anodic dissolution tests were performed utilizing aluminum foil as WE and an upper cut-off potential of 4 V vs. Na^+/Na . The measurements were done for both investigated electrolytes to allow for comparison. From Fig. S3a it can be seen that in NaPF₆ in EC:PC current is flowing in the first cycle but in the following cycles only negligible amounts of current are obtained. This indicates the formation of a stable passivation layer within the first cycle as expected from literature [21]. In the case of NaTFSI in TEG:PC large current densities of $\sim 60 \mu A cm^{-2}$ can be seen for each cycle. It seems like the aluminum is not protected in this electrolyte and thus, is slowly dissolved leading to the steady current flow. In order to find a more stable potential range for NaTFSI in TEG:PC, the same measurement was conducted with an upper cut-off potential of 3.8 V vs. Na^+/Na . As can be seen from Fig. S3b there is significant current flow in the first cycle but almost no current flow in the second cycle and beyond. Thus, as long as the positive cut-off potential does not surpass 3.8 V vs. Na^+/Na , the anodic dissolution of the Al current collector can be considered as negligible in NaTFSI in TEG:PC.

3.3. Sodium-ion Capacitor full-cells

After having investigated the corresponding half-cells, full-cells containing AC as positive and presodiated HC as negative electrode were assembled and tested. A very important parameter when building up full-cells is the mass loading and balancing of the electrodes. In literature, SIC realized using a “capacity balancing” of $q(HC)/q(AC) = 1.5$ showed good performances and good cycling stability [9]. Besides the capacity balancing, it is obviously important to consider the structural and mechanical stability of the electrodes at the targeted mass loadings. Keeping all this in mind, electrodes having mass loadings of $\sim 2\text{--}3 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$ were chosen and SICs displaying a mass balancing of $m(AC)/m(HC) = 1.4$ were assembled. Detailed information about the resulting capacity balancing is available in Fig. S4 and Table S1.

A key aspect for the realization of SICs is the presodiation of the HC electrode. Herein, an ex-situ electrochemical presodiation method [22] was employed, which is described in the experimental section of this work. The success of the presodiation step was investigated and is discussed in the supporting information (see Fig. S5).

The electrochemical performance of the assembled SICs was evaluated carrying out galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments. Fig. 4a shows a comparison of the capacity retention and coulombic efficiencies of SICs containing the two investigated electrolytes. The cells were

Fig. 4. Rate-test of SIC full-cells. Capacity and coulombic efficiency at different current densities (a) and corresponding Ragone plot (b). The current density, capacity, energy density and power density values are all normalized on the total mass of active materials.

Fig. 5. Float results of SICs. Capacity and coulombic efficiency (a) and potential profiles (b) for NaPF₆ in EC:PC (i, ii, iii) and NaTFSI in TEG:PC (iv, v, vi) at selected float times 0 h, 40 h and 100 h.

cycled between $1 \text{ V} < E_{\text{cell}} < 3.8 \text{ V}$. The reported values of capacity are normalized on the total mass of active material of the respective device. Qualitatively, the systems perform quite comparably, and both display good capacity values. It is however obvious that the NaPF_6 in EC:PC system reaches higher capacity values (e.g. 37 mA h g^{-1} vs. 25 mA h g^{-1} at 0.1 A g^{-1}). For both, in the first six cycles (at 25 mA g^{-1}) the discharge capacity is decreasing and coulombic efficiencies of 90–95 % are obtained. This rapid capacity loss is even more distinct for the “conventional” electrolyte. This could indicate a less stable SEI at the HC surface. For both electrolytes, higher rates lead to coulombic efficiencies of >95 %. From the rate-test the Ragone-plot, displaying the power and energy density of the devices, was determined (Fig. 4b). At 0.25 A g^{-1} the device containing NaPF_6 in EC:PC shows a power density of 925 W kg^{-1} and an energy density of 70 W h kg^{-1} . These values exceed others reported in literature for comparable lab scale SICs [9]. At the same current density, the system containing NaTFSI in TEG:PC displays 920 W kg^{-1} and 40 W h kg^{-1} . Overall, high performing SICs were realized with both electrolytes.

To investigate the stability of the SICs, float tests at $E_{\text{cell}} = 3.8 \text{ V}$ have been carried out for 100 h. These types of tests, although less frequently used than galvanostatic charge-discharge tests, are particularly helpful to understand the stability of high-power devices under stressful conditions. The resulting capacity and coulombic efficiency development during the floating tests are reported in Fig. 5a. The device containing NaPF_6 in EC:PC displays a steady loss of capacity, leading to 37 % capacity retention after 100 h. The SIC with NaTFSI in TEG:PC shows a remarkably different behavior. Initially, the device displays a slight increase in capacity, reaching its maximum at around 40 h of float time. Afterwards the capacity is rather stable and after 100 h the device retains 86 % of its initial capacity (72 % of maximum capacity). It is likely that the capacity increase in this latter device is due to an activation process within the cell. Considering these results, the SIC containing NaTFSI in TEG:PC appears to be more stable than the device containing the “conventional” electrolyte. In order to gain more insight into the occurrences within the cells, the potential profiles at selected float times (0 h, 40 h and 100 h) are shown in Fig. 5b.

For both devices typical voltage and potential profiles are obtained. The AC electrodes display triangular shapes as expected for the capacitive material. On the other hand, the HC electrodes show a slope followed by a plateau, which originate from the insertion/extraction of sodium-ions into/out of the material.

Firstly, the development of the SIC containing the “conventional” electrolyte will be discussed (Fig. 5b(i-iii)). As shown, at the beginning of the test (0 h) the HC electrode of the device containing NaPF_6 in EC:PC features a rather narrow plateau. The HC is very close to 0 V vs. Na^+/Na and not drifting much in potential during charge/discharge. Thus, in this device the AC is almost reaching 1 V vs. Na^+/Na in the discharge and 3.8 V vs. Na^+/Na in the charge process. At higher floating times the discharge time decreases, as expected from the loss in capacity. It is evident that the HC loses a lot of capacity as indicated by the less distinct plateau at 40 h of float time. After 100 h of floating almost no plateau is observable and the potential excursion of the HC has enlarged significantly (ca. 0–2 V vs. Na^+/Na). On the other hand, the potential range of the AC electrode decreased notably, and after 100 h of floating the electrode is ranging only between 3 and 3.8 V vs. Na^+/Na . It is also interesting to have a look at the electrode potentials during floating: As can be seen in Fig. S6a the longer the device is floated, the more both electrode potentials are shifted to higher values.

As shown in Fig. 5b(iv-vi) the potential profiles of the SIC containing NaTFSI in TEG:PC, and their evolution over the floating time, is significantly different. This device displays a higher resistance compared to the one discussed above and displays a lower initial capacity (as discussed for Fig. 5a). Differently from the previous case, in this device the AC electrode is working in a rather constant potential region over the whole duration of the floating experiment. At the beginning of the float test the HC electrode of this device is experiencing negative potentials

which might lead to sodium plating. Interestingly, after 40 h of floating the discharge time increases, correlating to the capacity increase observed in Fig. 5a. Negative potentials are reached for the HC here as well. From these potential profiles it is not possible to conclude without doubt the occurrence or lack thereof of plating. After 100 h of floating, the discharge only takes 15 min and the HC reaches negative potentials of up to -0.5 V vs. Na^+/Na at which plating is very likely. However, it is interesting to notice that even at this advanced stage of aging, the potential excursion experienced by the HC is only 1 V (between -0.5 and 0.5 V vs. Na^+/Na) and no significant potential drift to more positive values is observed (see Fig. S6b). Therefore, although subject to very low and potentially detrimental potentials, the HC electrode in this SIC displays a more stable behavior over the course of the measurement compared to that of the device containing NaPF_6 in EC:PC. This could correlate to the observation in Fig. 2d that HC half-cells displayed an enhanced cycle life with NaTFSI in TEG:PC. However, further proof is needed to securely conclude the origin of the different stabilities in the SIC floating tests. Therefore, the respective half-cells were built-up and floated at approximately the same conditions as in the full-cell. Thus, presodiated HC electrodes were floated at 5 mV vs. Na^+/Na and AC electrodes were floated at 3.8 V vs. Na^+/Na . The results in Fig. S7 show that the HC as well as the AC are both stable with both electrolytes for 100 h of floating time. Hence, the different aging behavior cannot be easily traced back to the individual half-cells but is rather an occurrence within the SIC full-cells.

Since electrochemical measurement techniques could not answer the question of why the SICs display such different floating stabilities depending on the electrolyte, a spectroscopic method was employed: Post-mortem XPS of the electrodes was conducted to analyze decomposition products, which accumulated on the HC and AC electrodes after the SIC floating test. Generally, AC electrodes contain less electrolyte decomposition products than HC electrodes. There is an increase in F content on AC electrodes after floating in the cells using both electrolyte systems (see Fig. 6 and Fig. S8 for AC XPS spectra).

More pronounced differences in the electrode surface compositions can be seen for the HCs after floating. HC from the cell using NaPF_6 in EC:PC exhibits a large amount of Na, F and O containing components (see Fig. S9 for HC O1s spectra). The C1s spectrum indicates the presence of C-F_x ($\sim 293.4 \text{ eV}$) [23] and oxygen-containing carbon functional groups, which can be found at binding energies in the range between 285 and 289 eV (see Fig. 7) [23]. The relative amounts of elements deposited on the HC using NaPF_6 in EC:PC to the HC using NaTFSI in TEG:PC indicate that NaTFSI in TEG:PC is more stable during floating and leads to less SEI formation. Moreover, the HC electrode using NaTFSI in TEG:PC exhibits more O containing decomposition products such as oxygenated carbon and NaOH (Na1s $\sim 1072.2 \text{ eV}$) [24] than F-containing components like NaF (F1s $\sim 684.4 \text{ eV}$) [25] or C-F_x, which are predominantly formed when using NaPF_6 in EC:PC. In particular the high amount of Na as surface-enriched element on HC potentially points to why the cell using NaPF_6 EC:PC leads to stronger loss of capacity during the floating experiment.

4. Conclusion

This work presented an in-depth comparison of a standard electrolyte for SIC application, NaPF_6 in EC:PC, with the novel electrolyte NaTFSI in TEG:PC. For the HC and AC half-cells rather comparable results in terms of capacity and capacitance were obtained. However, the HC cell showed increased cycle life with NaTFSI in TEG:PC. On the other hand, high rate cycling ($>20 \text{ A g}^{-1}$) led to significantly higher capacitance values for AC half-cells with NaPF_6 in EC:PC. The full-cell SICs displayed higher capacity and energy density values for NaPF_6 in EC:PC. In floating tests it was revealed that the NaTFSI in TEG:PC electrolyte stabilizes the SICs, leading to a higher cycle life in terms of capacity retention. Post-mortem XPS of the electrodes floated in SICs revealed significant differences at the HC surface depending on the electrolyte.

Fig. 6. Electrode surface compositions determined by XPS measurements. Pristine HC and AC electrodes were measured as well as the HC and AC electrodes which were floated within a SIC device with the respective electrolytes.

Fig. 7. XPS spectra C1s (a), F1s (b) and Na1s (c) of pristine and floated HC electrodes. The pristine electrode is depicted in black-gray colors, the electrode floated in a SIC with NaPF₆ in EC:PC in blue shades and the electrode floated in a SIC with NaTFSI in TEG:PC in green shades. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

The faster degradation of the NaPF₆ in EC:PC system could potentially be due to the increased formation of Na-containing compounds at the HC surface. All in all, NaTFSI in TEG:PC seems to be a very promising alternative electrolyte for SIC application.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Andrea Hainthaler: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Akshaya S. Sidharthan:** Investigation, Data curation. **Desirée Leistenschneider:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review &

editing. **Andrea Balducci**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powera.2024.100158>.

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